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Intrinsic Factors Influencing Primary School Teachers' Motivation

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Abstract

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This paper aims to examine the impact of intrinsic factors i.e., trust and recognition, on Primary School teachers' motivation. Various teachers from different campuses were selected as the respondents. It is proven from various studies that a range of factors affects the teachers' motivation level. It had been additionally important to get that there's an instantaneous and positive relationship between trust and recognition and employees' motivation. Hence, if trust and recognition offered to teachers, were to be altered, then there would be an opposite impact on teachers' motivation. Teachers' motivation is very crucial for the promotion of teaching and learning excellence. Motivated teachers most probably inspire students to learn new things, confirm the implementation of academic reforms, and feelings of satisfaction and fulfilment. Whereas teachers' motivation is instrumental in the learning and teaching process and a huge number of teachers are unmotivated. Proper attention should be paid to on this observation and ought to be investigating the factors that enhance teachers' motivation as motivation is crucial in attaining management goals in every organization.

Keywords:

Intrinsic factors, Motivation, Trust, Recognition.

Introduction

Motivation could be a term that refers to a human wanting to try to do the simplest potential job or to exert the most effort to perform assigned tasks. Motivation is the driving force that triggers the human to try to or not do one thing (Broussard, 2004). Motivation is imperative for associate organization's growth. Motivation creates productivity ensures structure potency and promotes loyalty among the staff. Motivation is vital in organizations and business activities because it is a particularly important element of the management method. No tangible result is possible without motivation. (Lewis, 1995) Declare that organization's energy is the outcome of its motivated employees. However, employees' capabilities are as vital as motivation in determining the performance. Committed and motivated employees can prove to be a driving force behind the success of an organization.

In the background of this study, motivation is described as an activity of making teachers feel that the tasks they perform are valued and recognized, and whatever rewards they get, be it certificate, or bonus are the outputs of their given inputs. (Owens, 2004) describes motivation as the factor that causes a person to behave in such way as he wants to do something. For the promotion of teaching and learning excellence in schools, teachers' motivation plays an instrumental role. Generally motivated teachers are a lot of probably to inspire students in the classrooms, to confirm the implementation of academic reforms, feelings of satisfaction and fulfillment. In one of the studies performed by (Ofoegbu, 2004) in Nigeria on: Teachers' motivation as a factor for classroom effectiveness and school improvement, he discovered that teachers' motivation plays important role in the effectiveness of classroom and overall improvement of the school. Several factors are found to impact teachers' motivation. Two major intrinsic factors that enhance teachers' motivation are Trust and Recognition.

Nowadays all organizations are keen to know the ways that how trust among employees can be improved in the organizations. Trust at workplace, is a recognized factor that is critical in increasing performance in organizations. Another factor, recognition also plays a vital role in teachers' motivation. Recognizing teachers for the work they do only cost some time and effort. This study particularly focuses on the impact on trust and recognition on primary school teachers' motivation at Air Foundation School system.

Objectives

- To know the impact of trust on Primary School teachers' motivation.
- To know the impact of recognition on Primary School teachers' motivation.
- To know the association between trust, recognition and motivation.

Research Objectives

1. To know the impact of trust on Primary School teachers' motivation.
2. To know the impact of recognition on Primary School teachers' motivation.
3. To know the association between trust, recognition and motivation.

Research Questions

1. What is the impact of trust on Primary School teachers' motivation?
2. What is the impact of recognition on Primary School teachers' motivation?
3. Is there any association between trust, recognition and motivation?

Literature review

Teachers' motivation: In the background of this study, motivation is described as an activity of making teachers feel that the tasks they perform are valued and recognized, and whatever rewards they get, be it certificate, or bonus are the outputs of their given inputs. (Peretomode, 1991) Defined motivation as a factor that stimulates the people to achieve certain goals in life. Motivation is thought to be the reason that triggers a person to perform certain activities. It is also considered as the

reason responsible for, why people decide to perform particular activity, how long they will be willing to carry out that activity, how hard they will perform to achieve it (Dorneyi, 2001). However, it is difficult to describe what motivation actually means (Chambers, 1999). (Robertson, 1985) Described motivation as a psychological concept that is related to the strength and direction of human behavior while (Vroom, 1995) defined motivation as stated to be the explanation of choice or direction. From the definitions given above, it is crystal clear that motivation is the driving force behind most of human activities. Motivation plays a crucial part in school as it is driving forces which increase teachers' performance and ultimately help the management to achieve their goals (Robbins, 2005). In a rapidly changing work environment, motivated employees are indispensable for the very survival of companies, organizations, and industries. Motivated employees are mean to be more productive and essential for organizational survival. Teachers in schools, if do not get enough motivation then they will possibly be less competent which in turn affects students and overall education system (Mustafa, 2010)

Trust and teachers' motivation: Trust represents a person's estimates of how likely he will be passionate about fulfilling organization's commitments. Trust creates a bond between employer and the employees which improves the motivation level of employees. Teachers' motivation is directly impacted favorably by the quality of organizational leadership and trust. The key element driving teachers' dedication and drive is trust. A supervisor's awareness of his subordinates' needs and feelings, according to Vroom, "has favorable consequences on their motivation to accomplish their tasks efficiently. In the context of education, Bryk and Schneider's mixed method study concluded that "relational trust" was

essential to school improvement. According to (Barnnet, 2004) among other researchers, trust encourages teachers to take more risks. Principal sincerity, frankness, and consistency are connected to teacher effort (Blase, 2000)

Recognition and teachers' motivation: A psychological sense of being acknowledged and valued for one's accomplishments is known as recognition. Recognition is one the essential components in uplifting employee job satisfaction level and motivation, which in turn positively add value to organizational success, according to Maurer (2001 June et al., 2006). In one of study by Kalimullah Khan, he examined the correlation between incentives and worker motivation, with one of the incentives being recognition. The findings revealed a substantial (0.65) correlation between employee work motivation and recognition (Kalimullah et al, 2010). Reward is the helpful tool that directly affects the employee's motivation and performance (Reena et al, 2009). Another empirical study was conducted in Pakistan to know the impact of recognition on employee's motivation by Rizwan which shows that there is significant relation between employee's recognition and motivation (Rizwan et al, 2010). The literature, studies, and discussion mentioned above fully support the first hypothesis, which states that rewarding employees' efforts motivates them to complete tasks and carry out duties assigned to them by the company. There are formal reward and recognition programs in place at many institutions, and libraries are no exception.

Research Model

Research Hypothesis

H 1: There is positive and significant impact of trust on primary school teachers' motivation.

H2: There is positive and significant impact of recognition on primary school teachers' motivation.

H3: There is positive and significant association between trust, recognition and motivation.

Research Methodology

Data Collection: A survey questionnaire was used to gather the data. In light of the study's intrinsic component influencing primary school teachers' drive to comprehend its implications A quantitative technique was used, and when (250) questionnaires were circulated and 248 of them were collected for analysis, 99% of the distributed questionnaires were used. Both primary and secondary data sources provided the information that was used in the study. In order to acquire insight into the research issue, the primary sources include direct data that was gathered through the distribution of questionnaires. Journals and other pertinent publications, both online and offline, are among the secondary data sources. Teachers at Air Foundation School System were given questionnaires to complete, which was how the data were collected. The whole content of the questionnaires was structured, and some of the questions were meant to evaluate previously developed study hypotheses.

The questionnaire created for this study comprises two sections, the first of which is made up of typical scale questions that ask about respondents' demographics. Later, the data was transformed into a percentage to facilitate analysis. The second half, which comprises of questions with five possible answers on 5-point Like Scales. Respondents are given the options to indicate how much they agree or disagree with the questions. The five choices were

provided to respondents to indicate the rate at that they agree or disagree the given queries. The answer choices provided for the queries begin with one – that stands for "Strongly Disagree", followed by two – that represents "Disagree", following is three – that signify "Neutral", followed by four – that represents "Agree" and ends with five – that stands for "Strongly Agree".

Population:

In Pakistan, the Air Foundation School System employs 3500 instructors in total. Therefore, it would be nearly impossible to survey every college for this study. In order to select a representative sample from the entire population and perform the research, this study employed a practical sampling technique. 250 teachers working at several campuses made up the study's sample. The sample size was determined after rejections due to incomplete responses, and the respondents were chosen based on their desire and convenience to reply to the survey.

Results

Utilizing statistical analysis tools, the collected data was examined. The data was examined using SPSS version 21 (Statistical Package for Social Sciences). The descriptive statistics, including correlation and regression analysis, as well as a comparison of the variances in the regression coefficient, were carried out using the SPSS program. The method for data analysis was used, and it uses Pearson's Correlation Coefficient. The technique was used to investigate the link between teachers' motivation and trust and recognition.

Frequency distribution

Frequency tables given below, provide the information about gender, age and qualifications of the respondents.

Frequency Table- Gender

	Trust	Recognition	Motivation
Trust Pearson Correlation	1	.432*	.328*
Sig. (2-tailed)		.005	.001
N	247	247	247
Recognition Pearson Correlation	.433*	1	.590*
Sig. (2-tailed)	.005		.001
N	247	247	247
Motivation Pearson Correlation	.328*	.590*	1
Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
N	247	247	247

Table 1 shows that out of 248 respondents, 122 were male which constitutes 49.2% and 126 (50.8%) were female

Frequency Table-2 Age

	Frequency	Percent
Valid 25-30 years	122	49.2
31-35 years	126	50.8
Total	248	100.0

Table-2 shows that out of 248 respondents, 122 (49.2%) were between the age of 25-30 years and other 126 (50.8%) were between the age of 31-35 years.

Frequency Table-3 Higher Degree

	Frequency	Percent
Valid Bachelor	115	46.3
Master	133	53.6
Total	248	100.0

Table-3 show that the qualifications of 115 (46.3%) out of 248 respondents were Bachelor and 133 (53.6%) were Master degree holders.

Reliability Test

	Frequency	Percent
Valid Male	122	49.2
Female	126	50.8
Total	248	100.0

Reliability Table-4

Cronbach's Alpha	N of items
.683	12

Table 04, indicates about the reliability of the scale, (the threshold value of the reliability is acceptable when it is more than 0.6)

H3: There is positive and significant association between trust, recognition and motivation.

In order to know the association between trust, recognition and motivation Pearson correlation test was performed.

Correlations Matrix Table-5

Correlation indicates that either the variables are positively related to each other, or there is any negative relationship. In this way these results also verify the hypothesis on the basis of the significant positive and negative relationship. If there is any of the correlation with negative sign, it indicates the negative relationship among those variables. Table 5 indicates the results of correlations, which express the relationship between all of the scale's variables, Hence there is positive association between Trust, recognition and motivation. Therefore first hypothesis of study is significant.

H 1: There is positive and significant impact of trust on primary school teachers' motivation.

H2: There is positive and significant impact of recognition on primary school teachers' motivation

Model summary Table-6

Model	R	R squared	Adjusted R square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.90 ^a	.480	.000	1.66846	.135

Dependent variable: Motivation

Table 6 indicates the results of Model Summary (Regression analysis), in this table the value of R (Multiple correlation coefficient), is 0.90, which is less solid relationship between the dependent variable (Motivation) and independent variables (Trust and Recognition). Further the model fitness (Std Error of the Estimate) is about 16.6%, which indicates that there is a gap of 83.4% which can be covered by introducing various other variables, and their applicability in various fields.

ANOVA Table-7

Model	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	C	Sig.
1 Regression	5.528	2	2.764	.993	.002 ^b
Residual	676.456	243	2.784		
Total	681.984	245			

Dependent Variable: Motivation

Independent variables: Trust and Recognition, Table 8 indicates the result of analysis of the variance of mean. The ANOVA table represents the overall significance of the model,

Coefficients a Table -8

Model	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1(Constant)	16.024	.632		25.337	.000
Trust	.002	.034	.004	.069	.000
Recognition	.068	.048	.090	1.403	.000

Table indicates the results of the coefficients, In the results of model summary the value of adjusted R square, (000), which indicates that the independent variable Motivation have 0% variance between the independent variables Trust and Recognition. Further this table also indicates that how much independent variable are inclined towards the dependent variable. The ratio is as; Trust 0.04%, and Recognition is 0.9%, both of the values indicates that the inclination of the share of independent variables towards dependent variable is negative. Further the hypothesis relating to these variables are also rejected and null hypothesis are accepted, because the given value is more than the threshold value (0.05).

Conclusion

The primary goal of this study was to determine how intrinsic factors such as trust and recognition affected primary school teachers' motivation at Air Foundation School System. Following a literature analysis and a study on the motivation of instructors at the Air Foundation School System, two key factors were picked for further investigation. Two theories were established with the goal of determining how Trust and Recognition affect Primary School Teachers' Motivation. The results of the regression analysis demonstrated a strong correlation between teachers' motivation and trust. The motivation level of teachers was found to be

significantly influenced by trust and recognition. The findings of this study are consistent with those of Kalimullah (et al, 2010), who found a substantial ($r=0.65$) correlation between employee work motivation and recognition. Similar to Vroom (1964, p. 213), who states that "concern by a supervisor for the needs and feelings of his subordinates has good effects on their motivation to execute their tasks efficiently," the findings from this study are consistent with his findings. Results show that trust directly enhances the motivation level of teachers. If teachers are trusted by their employer, they are more likely to perform well and accomplish their targets effectively. In addition to trust, recognition also plays crucial role in teachers' motivation. When teachers are recognized by their employer, they are ready to put extra efforts in their work. Moreover, these two intrinsic factors i.e. Trust and recognition, not only enhances the motivation level of the teachers but also increases the job satisfaction among them.

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